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SAN BUENAVENTURA ELEMENTARY SCHOOL

**PROJECT S.M.A.R.T. (STARTING TO MOLD ACCELERATED READERS
WITH TECHNOLOGY): READING LEVEL ENHANCEMENT OF GRADE 2
PUPILS IN SAN BUENAVENTURA ELEMENTARY SCHOOL,
DISTRICT OF STO. ANGEL - DIVISION OF
SAN PABLO CITY**

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ABSTRACT

The purpose of the study is to find out whether Project S.M.A.R.T., an innovation that utilize offline mobile application created by the researcher namely “Unang Hakbang sa Pagbasa” that will serve as the pupils’ supplementary reading materials can help the grade two pupils of San Buenaventura ES of Sto. Angel District for S.Y. 2022-2023 to enhance their reading level. This study was experimental in nature that utilized a total of 52 through purposive sampling technique. Descriptive statistics such as frequency and percentage were used to analyze and interpret the results.

The findings revealed that Project S.M.A.R.T. help pupils to enhance their reading level. The pre- and post-assessment tool devised by the division used in Reading Journey program was utilized to find out the result. The result shows a positive result as the number of non-readers, frustration and instructional decreased while number of independent readers increased.

This research was essential because we are solving the learning gaps through focusing first on students’ literacy. One factor that can aid this was to provide reading materials that are accessible. This research supports the STRATA framework of the Division of San Pablo City which is the integration of technology in reading and numeracy activities. As well as the SIP of San Buenaventura ES, the E-SBES which develop students' skills in literacy and numeracy to attain learning standards.

Keywords: *reading level, offline application, enhancement, supplementary, mobile application*

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CONTEXT AND RATIONALE

Reading is an important skill that every learner must acquire. So many studies shows that reading helps students to develop higher attention and lead to understanding concepts related to their academics. Because of the COVID-19 pandemic, it affects how teachers help the pupils gain mastery on reading as well as the pupils acquires the skill.

Based on assessment done on the previous school year, most of the students don't have enough reading materials at home aside from the activity sheets and modules given to them. A greater number of the students' population has also no access on internet where they can search for materials that they can use in practicing their reading. Therefore, one strategy that can be done is to provide supplementary reading materials that they can use at home without using the internet.

In line with this, digital technology plays a vital role in producing instructional materials that the students can utilize at home even without internet connection. Considering the result of the assessment, Project SMART (**S**tarting to **M**old **A**ccelerated **R**eaders with **T**echnology) is an innovation that utilize offline mobile application namely "Unang Hakbang sa Pagbasa" that will serve as the learners' supplementary reading materials that they can use in practicing reading.

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The said mobile application was designed and developed by the researcher/ proponent after attending the webinar entitled “Webinar Session on the Use and Development of Aklatech 3.0- Book of the Future” held last July 23, 2022. Aside from reading lessons, it also includes interactive activities that the pupils can answer that will assess not only the progress of their reading skill but also their comprehension. This offline application was created through Adobe Software and different multimedia tools such as Canva, Web Designer, Lumi and Java Application. The said program was implemented on the first week of February, 2023.

This research was essential, especially because we are amid establishing a new system for providing high-quality education to our pupils that focuses most especially on numeracy as well as literacy, specifically the enhancement of reading level. One factor that can aid the achievement of goal was to provide reading materials that are accessible to everyone.

This research also supports the STRATA framework of the Division of San Pablo City which is the T that stands for Technology or the integration of technology in reading and numeracy activities.

As well as the school implementation program of San Buenaventura ES, the E-SBES which is the S stands for Students' skills in literacy and numeracy to attain learning standards. As cited by Hasselbring & Bausch (2005), as educators, we must raise our awareness of the role that technology plays in learning especially on enhancing literacy skill of the pupils.

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INNOVATION, INTERVENTION AND STRATEGY

Academic performance is dependent on grade-level reading proficiency. Children start to read early on, and as they grow older, they read to learn. Reading difficulties before the end of third grade might lead to continued academic difficulties, as many topics rely on written texts. A good reader can understand difficult information, examine concepts, think critically, and excel academically. (United Way of Central Georgia, 2023)

Based on assessment done on the previous school year, most of the students don't have enough reading materials at home aside from the activity sheets and modules given to them. A greater number of the students' population has also no access on internet where they can search for materials that they can use in practicing their reading. Therefore, one strategy that can be done is to provide supplementary reading materials that they can use at home without using the internet.

In the proposed study, the researcher wants to determine whether PROJECT S.M.A.R.T. (Starting to Mold Accelerated Readers with Technology) can aid in enhancing the reading level of Grade 2 pupils categorized as instructional, frustration and on-readers in San Buenaventura Elementary School. The objective of the said project are as follows: (1) Increase the pupils' reading level in Filipino which can help them develop higher level of attention in their reading skills and wider understanding in the concepts related to their

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academics. (2) Provide supplementary reading materials that are flexible and accessible for every pupil even without the use of internet connection. Lastly, (3) enhance the pupils' reading skills through the utilization of offline application.

The intervention, innovation and strategy will follow the following:

1. Project **SMART (Starting to Mold Accelerated Readers with Technology)**- implemented to Non-reader and Frustration pupils during 3:30 to 4:00 in the afternoon after class at home with the guidance of their parents/ guardians.
2. Assembly and Orientation Programme - Meet the parents and pupils to introduce and explain the purpose of the project / program to be implemented.
3. Daily Attendance of parents and pupils will be closely monitor and collect.
4. **SMART** Reading – This will be conducted 30 minutes at home by the pupils by the guidance of their parents/ guardians. This is divided into different parts. These are the list of scheduled lessons to be practice by the pupils:
 - *Part 1* – Lessons 1-3
 - *Part 2* – Lessons 4-6
 - *Part 3* – Lessons 7-9
 - *Part 4* – Lessons 10-12
 - *Part 5* – Lessons 13-15
 - *Part 6* – Lessons 16-18

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- *Part 7* – Lessons 19-21
 - *Part 8* – Lessons 22-24
 - *Part 9* – Lessons 25-26
5. Material to be used- an offline mobile application entitled “Unang Hakbang sa Pagbasa” created using Adobe Software and different multimedia tools such as Canva, Web Designer, Lumi and Java Application.
6. Installation and dissemination of the offline mobile application- The offline mobile application will be installed on the students’ gadget using either of the two ways: First, the installer of the offline mobile application will be sent through Facebook messenger where the parents will download and install on their gadgets. Second, they can go to school for the teacher to assist them in installing the offline mobile application.

Copy of Offline Mobile Application:

<https://drive.google.com/file/d/1KfQkMEZoUcN3coBfoLoThcFiXrsjmZi8/view?usp=sharing>

ACTION RESEARCH QUESTIONS

This study aims to determine the effects of Project S.M.A.R.T. in enhancing the reading level of Grade 2 pupils categorized as instructional, frustration and non-readers in San Buenaventura Elementary school, Sto. Angel District - Division of San Pablo City.

Specifically, the study seeks answers to the following:

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1. What is the reading level of Grade 2 pupils on pre-assessment in San Buenaventura Elementary School?
2. Is there a significant difference in the reading level of the Grade 2 pupils before and after the reading intervention?
3. How effective is Project S.M.A.R.T in enhancing the reading level of Grade 2 pupils categorized as instructional, frustration and non-readers in San Buenaventura Elementary school?

ACTION RESEARCH METHODS

This research is experimental in nature, a scientific approach employing two variables. In this case, the first variable is said to be the reading level of the pupils and the second variable is the Project S.M.A.R.T. (**S**tarting to **M**old **A**ccelerated **R**eaders with **T**echnology), the said two variables are measured and tested if there are differences.

A. Participants and/or Other Sources of Data Information

There were 52 respondents for the study. These respondents are (7) non-readers, (31) frustration readers, and (14) instructional readers of Grade 2 pupils in San Buenaventura Elementary School, Sto. Angel District – Division of San Pablo City for school year 2022-2023

B. Data Gathering Methods

This research used a purposive sampling technique. Purposive sampling, also known as judgmental, selective, or subjective sampling, is a type of non-

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probability sampling in which researchers choose respondents to participate in the study based on their own judgment. Since the purpose of this study was to find out whether the offline mobile application can help pupils enhance their reading level by using it as supplementary material, the pupils who are categorized as non-readers, frustration, and instructional are chosen to become the respondents of the study.

For the collection of data, this research used an offline mobile application entitled “Unang Hakbang sa Pagbasa”, a learners’ supplementary reading material that they can use in practicing reading. The said mobile application was designed and developed by the researcher/ proponent. Another instrument utilized was the pre-assessment and post-assessment tool devised by the Division of San Pablo City under Reading Journey Program. The said instruments were used to collect data from the respondents to find out whether the said intervention was effective or not.

C. Data Analysis

This research used descriptive statistics such as frequency and percentage. Frequency and percentage are descriptive statistics that illustrate how frequently a category appears in a data collection and how much of the data set it represents. The result of the pre-assessment and post-assessment was compared to find out the results.

The researcher first developed the research paradigm having Project S.M.A.R.T. (**S**tarting to **M**old **A**ccelerated **R**eaders with **T**echnology) as input

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and Grade 2 Reading Level as the output. This is based on the conceptual framework supported by models and related literature. After determining the statement of the problem and the research hypotheses, the instrument was constructed.

To ensure the validity and reliability of the instrument, the offline mobile application was assessed by the school's LR coordinator, master teacher and school head. On the other hand, the pre-assessment and post-assessment tool used was the same as the instrument used in Reading Journey program which was devised and assessed by different experts. After the assessment and revision, the researcher asked permission from the school head for the conduct of the study.

The assistance of the Grade 2 advisers is requested to ensure success of the distribution of the research instrument as well as gathering the data needed. Then, the researcher retrieved data. Thereafter, the data were gathered and was organized, classified, tabulated, analyzed and interpreted.

DISCUSSION OF RESULTS AND REFLECTION

The results are presented in a pie chart form as well as the corresponding analysis and the interpretation of the data. This research aims to find out whether Project S.M.A.R.T. an innovation that utilize offline mobile

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application namely “Unang Hakbang sa Pagbasa” that will serve as the pupils’ supplementary reading materials that they can use in practicing reading can help the grade two pupils of San Buenaventura Elementary School, Sto. Angel District- Division of San Pablo City for school year 2022-2023 enhance their reading level.

Figure 1. Distribution of Respondents according to their Reading Level on Reading Journey Pre-Assessment for S.Y. 2022-2023

Figure 1 presents the distribution of respondents according to their reading levels during the Reading Journey Pre-Assessment for School Year 2022–2023. The data reveal that the majority of learners, comprising 31 respondents or 60%, were classified under the frustration reading level. This indicates that most pupils experienced significant difficulty in reading independently, demonstrating limited comprehension and fluency when exposed to grade-level texts. Learners under this level generally require

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intensive teacher support, guided reading activities, and targeted interventions to improve their foundational reading skills.

Meanwhile, 14 respondents or 27% were categorized under the instructional reading level. This suggests that a considerable portion of the learners were able to read with partial understanding when provided with teacher guidance and appropriate instructional support. Although these learners exhibited better reading ability compared to those in the frustration level, they still needed continuous scaffolding, comprehension exercises, and vocabulary enhancement activities to reach the independent reading level.

On the other hand, only 7 respondents or 13% were identified as non-readers. While this group represents the smallest percentage, it still signifies the presence of learners who have not yet developed basic decoding and word recognition skills. These learners may require more intensive remediation programs, phonemic awareness training, and individualized reading interventions to address their literacy gaps.

Overall, the findings imply that the reading proficiency of the respondents was generally below the expected level, as a large majority fell under the frustration category and none were identified as independent readers. The results highlight the urgent need for strengthened reading intervention programs, differentiated instruction, and consistent literacy support within the school. Programs such as remedial reading sessions, guided reading activities, use of leveled reading materials, and parental

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involvement initiatives may help improve learners' reading performance and gradually move them toward higher reading proficiency levels.

Figure 2. Distribution of Respondents according to their Reading Level on Reading Journey Post-Assessment for S.Y. 2022-2023

Figure 2 illustrates the distribution of respondents according to their reading levels during the Reading Journey Post-Assessment for School Year 2022–2023. The results show a noticeable improvement in the reading performance of the learners compared to the pre-assessment results. The largest group of respondents, consisting of 12 learners or 52%, reached the instructional reading level. This indicates that more than half of the learners were already capable of reading with better comprehension and fluency when provided with minimal teacher guidance and instructional support. The increase in the number of learners under this category suggests that the reading interventions and literacy activities implemented during the program were effective in enhancing the learners' reading abilities.

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Furthermore, 9 respondents or 39% remained under the frustration reading level. Although this still represents a considerable portion of the class, the percentage significantly decreased compared to the pre-assessment findings. This implies that several learners were able to progress from frustration level to instructional level after exposure to reading remediation programs, guided reading sessions, and other literacy enhancement activities. However, learners in this category may still require continuous support, differentiated instruction, and regular reading practice to further improve their comprehension and fluency skills.

Meanwhile, only 2 respondents or 9% were classified as non-readers. This reduction from the pre-assessment result demonstrates a positive improvement in the basic reading skills of the learners. The decrease in the number of non-readers indicates that the intervention strategies helped struggling readers develop foundational skills such as letter recognition, decoding, and word reading.

Overall, the post-assessment results reflect substantial progress in the reading proficiency of the respondents. The increase in learners under the instructional level and the decline in both frustration-level readers and non-readers suggest that the Reading Journey intervention program contributed positively to the development of learners' literacy skills. The findings further emphasize the importance of sustained reading programs, individualized

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interventions, and consistent monitoring to ensure continuous improvement and eventually move learners toward independent reading proficiency.

Based on the findings of the study, it was concluded that Project S.M.A.R.T. can help the Grade 2 pupils enhance their reading level was accepted. The result of pre-assessment and post-assessment conducted shows a positive result as the number of non-readers, frustration and instructional decreased while number of independent readers increased. This implies that the Project S.M.A.R.T. was an effective innovation program as it helps on enhancing pupils' reading level.

In the light of the findings and conclusions of the study the following recommendation were set forth:

Administrations. They may consider conducting relevant training and seminars that will make the school heads and teachers cope with new strategies and methodologies specifically about the enhancement of pupils' reading level that is relevant and needed nowadays.

School heads. They may be able to provide assistance to the teachers in devising, planning, and implementing plans, methodologies and strategies that will help on the enhancement of pupils' reading level.

Teachers. They may be able to provide assistance to their pupils based on their needs such as providing reading supplementary materials that are accessible and effective. They may also be able to devise reading materials that can help the pupils.

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Future Researchers. They may be able to find out new programs, interventions and projects that will help on the enhancement of pupils' reading level that are applicable on their current needs.

ACTION PLAN

Activities	Output	Date of Implementation	Person Involved	Budget	Budget source
Conducting School Learning Action Cell related to the use of offline mobile application in enhancing reading level of pupils	Documentation Attendance M&E	School Year 2023-2024	School Head, Master Teacher and Teachers	None	None
Conducting Focal Group Discussions related to the use of offline mobile application in enhancing reading level of pupils	Documentation Attendance M&E	School Year 2023-2024	School Head, Master Teacher and Teachers	None	None

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